

pH-Metric Studies on the Metal (Vanadyl and Thorium) Pyrophosphate Reaction

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The interaction of VO^{2+} and Th^{4+} ions with pyrophosphoric acid has been studied by potentiometric technique. pH-titrations of reaction mixtures containing metal salt and pyrophosphoric acid have provided evidence for the formation of metal ligand chelate containing metal ion and pyrophosphoric acid in the molar ratio of 1 : 2 and 2 : 1. From the analysis of pH-metric data, various reaction steps including polymerisation of 1 : 2 (metal : pyrophosphate) in the high pH-range have been suggested. The values of the stability constant β , for VO^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes were found to be 0.370×10^{12} and 0.400×10^{12} respectively.

A NUMBER of workers¹⁻¹¹ carried out the potentiometry of uranium ion with different ligands and their dimerisation, trimerisation constants were determined. On the same line we planned to determine the extent of polymerisation of the complexes of vanadyl and thorium ions with pyrophosphoric acid.

In the present paper, we report the results of pH-metric studies on the reaction products of vanadyl and thorium ions with pyrophosphoric acid.

Experimental

Reagents and Solutions :

All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade (BDH) except pyrophosphoric acid which was of MERCK products. All the solutions were made in conductivity water. The sets of mixtures titrated against standard KOH solution were 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 2 : 1, 1 : 3, 1 : 4, 1 : 8 and 1 : 16 (metal : pyrophosphate) but fruitful results were achieved only with 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 mixtures.

Procedure :

The mixture prepared were taken in a round bottomed three necked flask and CO_2 -free air was bubbled through it continuously¹². Then stepwise titrations were made with standard (0.1M) KOH.

Results and Discussion

Determination of dissociation constants of pyrophosphoric acid :

The procedure employed by Speakman¹³ for the determination of constants is used. The values of PK_{al} (first dissociation constant) and pK_{a2} (second disso-

ciation constant) of $H_4P_2O_7$ from Fig. 1 were found to be 1.0104 and 1.9732. These values of pK 's are in close agreement with a value of 1.0 and 2.0 reported by Davies and Monk¹⁴.

Reactions of metal salt and pyrophosphoric acid :

Curve 1 (Fig. 2) for the pH-metric titration of an equimolar mixture of vanadyl chloride and pyrophosphoric acid with KOH, exhibit sharp inflexion points at $m=2\frac{2}{3}$ and $m=1\frac{1}{3}$ respectively, where m represents moles of KOH added per metal ion. Curve O (Fig. 2) for the titration of $H_4P_2O_7$ with KOH exhibits inflexion points at $m=1\frac{2}{3}$ and $m=3.0$. Similarly the m values for thorium pyrophosphate system may be determined from Fig. 3. The reaction at the first inflexion point may be written as :

The second inflexion point may be written in accordance with the following equation,

The m values for Th^{4+} were found to be different from VO^{2+} due to polymerisation effects.

1 : 1 metal-pyrophosphoric acid reaction

Equilibrium constants :

In the initial stages, the reaction may be represented as :

Fig 1 - Graphical representation of the dissociation constant of pyrophosphoric acid.

$$X = \frac{[H^+](T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+])}{2T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+]}, \quad Y = \frac{[H^+]^2(T_{OH} + [H^+])}{2T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+]}$$

with Th^{4+} ions, the reaction may be represented as :

where H_4A represents the pyrophosphoric acid. The equilibrium constant K_1 of the reaction may be expressed as :

$$K_1 = \frac{[VOH_2A][H^+]^2}{[VO^{2+}][H_4A]} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

For other metal system

$$K_1 = \frac{[ThH_2A]^{2+}[H^+]^2}{[Th^{4+}][H_4A]} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

In order to account for the hydrolysed species of the free metal ions for the equilibrium studies, the values of hydrolysis constants, viz.,

$$K_{h1} = \frac{[VO(OH)^+][H^+]^2}{[VO^{2+}]} = 10^{-6.0} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$\text{and } K_{h2} = \frac{[VO(OH)}_2^{2+}][H^+]^2}{[VO^{2+}]} = 10^{-6.88} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

as reported by Rossotti and Rossotti¹⁵ have been used. If T_M represents the total concentration of all the metal species, T_A that of various ligand species and T_{OH} the concentration of the base added to the reaction mixture during the titration, the following equations for maintaining the material

balance are obtained :

$$T_M = [VO^{2+}] + [VO(OH)^+] + 2[VO(OH)}_2^{2+}] + [VOH_2A] \dots\dots(7)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = [VO(OH)^+] + 2[VO(OH)}_2^{2+}] + 2[VOH_2A] + [H_3A^-] + 2[H_2A^{2-}] \dots\dots(8)$$

$$T_A = [VOH_2A] + [H_4A] + [H_3A^-] + [H_2A^{2-}] \dots\dots(9)$$

In the pH range studied, OH^- was taken to be negligible as compared to the concentrations of other species present in the reaction mixture. Since $T_M = T_A$ in 1 : 1 system, the elimination of $[VO(OH)^+]$, $[VO(OH)}_2^{2+}]$ and $[VOH_2A]$ between the equations (7) - (9) gives :

$$2T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+] = [VO^{2+}] + [H_4A] - [H_2A^{2-}] \dots\dots(10)$$

and combining equations for ka_1, ka_2

$$\left[k_{a1} = \frac{[H_3A^-][H^+]}{[H_4A]}, \quad k_{a2} = \frac{[H_2A^{2-}][H^+]}{[H_3A^-]} \right]$$

the dissociation constants for $H_4P_2O_7$ and (7) and (9), it can be shown that :

$$[H_4A] = \frac{[VO^{2+}] + [VO(OH)^+] + 2[VO(OH)}_2^{2+}]}{\left[1 + \frac{ka_1}{[H^+]} + \frac{ka_1 \cdot ka_2}{[H^+]^2} \right]} \dots\dots(11)$$

Elimination of $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})^+]$, $[\{\text{VO}(\text{OH})\}_2^{2+}]$ and $[\text{VOH}_2\text{A}]$ and

$$[\text{VO}^{2+}] = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 + 4ac}}{2a} \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

between equations (5)–(8) gives :

$$\frac{2 \times 10^{-6.88}}{[\text{H}^+]^2} [\text{VO}^{2+}]^2 + \left[2 + \frac{10^{-6.0}}{[\text{H}^+]} \right] [\text{VO}^{2+}] - [2T_M - T_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+]] = 0 \dots(12)$$

where

$$a = \frac{2 \times 10^{-6.88}}{[\text{H}^+]^2}, \quad b = 2 + \frac{10^{-6.0}}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

$$c = 2T_M - T_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+]$$

The values of equilibrium constants K_1 for both the systems are computed and presented in table 1.

TABLE—1 pH-TITRATIONS OF VANADYL CHLORIDE + PYROPHOSPHORIC ACID

Temperature $30 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$

Vol. of KOH ml.	VO ²⁺ —pyrophosphoric acid system								
	1 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 1)			1 : 2 (Fig. 2, curve 2)			2 : 1 (Fig. 2, curve 4)		
	pH	pK ₁	pkH ₁	pH	pK ₂	β × 10 ²	α	pH	pK _s
0.0	2.75	1.59	1.34	2.50	0.16	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.370	3.0	2.65
0.50	2.50	2.17	0.59	2.75	0.16	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.365	3.0	2.65
1.0	2.60	1.94	0.89	2.75	0.15	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.365	3.10	2.31
1.5	2.80	1.47	1.49	2.95	0.14	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.355	3.45	2.62
2.0	3.0	0.99	2.09	3.25	0.13	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.340	4.40	1.72
2.5	3.65	0.63	4.04	4.30	0.11	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.320	5.25	1.32
3.0	5.15	4.70	8.54	5.55	0.97	× 10 ⁻⁸	0.300	6.60	0.26
3.5	6.0	7.15	11.09	6.35	0.92	× 10 ⁻⁴	0.295	7.90	1.74
4.0	7.05	10.24	14.24	7.35	0.85	× 10 ⁻⁴	0.290	8.45	1.03
4.5	7.85	12.62	16.64	8.10	0.86	× 10 ⁻⁴	0.293	9.50	3.56

Fig. 2—Potentiometric titrations of vanadyl-pyrophosphate system with KOH(0.1M). Curves 1,2,3 & 4 represent titration of vanadyl-pyrophosphoric acid mixtures 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 & 2 : 1 respectively. Curves O & O' represent titrations of pyrophosphoric acid (0.001M and vanadyl chloride (0.001M) respectively. m = moles of KOH added per metal ion. Ionic strength 1M(KCl). Total volume of the solution taken = 50 ml.

(1 : 2) metal-pyrophosphoric acid reaction :

When two molecules of pyrophosphoric acid are titrated in the presence of single molecule of vanadyl chloride, two sharp inflexions at $m=2\frac{1}{2}$ and at $m=4\frac{1}{2}$ are observed and this may be attributed to the formation of 1 : 2 complex in accordance with the equation :

Writing the equation for equilibrium constant K_a and material balance equations (using the same method as in 1 : 1 system) and on simplification, the final equation may be expressed as :

$$a[VO^{2+}]^2 - b[VO^{2+}] + c = 0 \quad \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

where

$$a = \frac{2K_{H1}}{[H^+]^2}$$

$$b = 2 \left[2 + \frac{k_{a1}}{[H^+]} \right] + \left[4 T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+] \right] \left[\frac{K_2}{[H^+]^2} + \frac{K_{H1}}{[H^+]^2} \right]$$

$$c = \left[4 T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+] \right] \left[1 + \frac{k_{a1}}{[H^+]} + \frac{k_{a1} \cdot k_{a2}}{[H^+]^2} \right]$$

The stability constant β of the overall reaction may be calculated from the following equation :

$$\beta = \frac{K_a}{k_{a1} \cdot k_{a2}} \quad \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

The values of pK_a and β calculated for vanadyl and thorium systems are presented in tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Reaction between metal salt and pyrophosphoric acid (2 : 1) :

Curve 4, Fig. 1 shows the pH-metric titration of solution of 2 : 1 mixture of vanadyl and pyrophosphoric acid with KOH. This curve exhibits a sharp

inflexion at $1\frac{1}{10}$ and $4\frac{3}{10}$ equivalent of base. The reaction is represented as :

Fig. 3—Potentiometric titrations of Thorium nitrate-pyrophosphate system with KOH (0.1M). Curves 1, 2, 3 & 4 represent titration of thorium nitrate-pyrophosphoric acid mixtures 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 & 2 : 1 respectively. Curve O & O' represent titrations of pyrophosphoric acid (0.001M) and thorium nitrate (0.001M) respectively. m = moles of KOH added per metal ion. Ionic strength = 1M (KNO₃).

The final expressions in this case may be written as follows :

$$[H_4A] = \frac{4 T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+]}{\left[2 + \frac{k_{a1}}{[H^+]} \right]} \quad \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

and

$$[VO^{2+}] = \frac{\left[3 T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+] \right] \left[1 + \frac{k_{a1}}{[H^+]} \right] - T_M}{\left[2 + \frac{k_{a1}}{[H^+]} \right]} \quad \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

TABLE—2 pH-METRIC TITRATIONS OF THORIUM NITRATE + PYROPHOSPHORIC ACID

Temperature 30±0.5°C.

Volume of KOH	1 : 1 TH ⁴⁺ —H ₄ P ₂ O ₇ system (Fig. 3, curve 1)			1 : 2 TH ⁴⁺ —H ₄ P ₂ O ₇ system (Fig. 3, curve 2)			2 : 1 Th ⁴⁺ —H ₄ P ₂ O ₇ system (Fig. 3, curve 4)		
	pH	PK ₂	pK _{H1}	pH	PK ₂	β × 10 ²	pH	PK ₂	pK _s
0.0	3.20	0.20	2.69	3.25	0.130 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.400	2.85	2.40	
0.50	2.90	1.23	1.79	3.10	0.13 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.450	2.90	2.45	
1.0	2.85	1.35	1.64	3.00	0.138 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.500	2.90	2.42	
1.5	2.90	1.23	1.79	3.00	0.137 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.512	3.0	2.45	
2.0	3.00	0.99	2.09	3.15	0.132 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.505	4.2	1.39	
2.5	3.25	0.37	2.84	4.00	0.113 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.395	5.8	0.31	
3.0	3.45	0.13	3.44	5.2	0.103 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.380	6.1	1.12	
3.5	4.45	2.75	6.44	6.60	0.10 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.360	6.3	1.56	
4.0	6.30	8.03	11.99	7.35	0.95 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.340	6.8	1.86	
4.5	7.00	10.10	14.09	8.00	0.92 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.322	7.3	2.53	

The values of K_s (for both vanadyl and thorium systems) are presented in tables 1 and 2 respectively.

Conclusions :

- 1) 1 : 1 chelates are not likely to be found since the pK_1 values are not constant over the entire pH-range. No constancy in the pK_{H1} values is observed for the corresponding complex thereby showing that polymerisation through hydroxyl groups is not possible.
- 2) The pK_2 and pK_3 values for the equilibrium studies with 1 : 2 and 2 : 1 mixtures show constancy in the pH range 2.5-5.5 (for vanadyl system), 3.25-5.2 (for thorium system) for 1 : 2 reaction and 3.0-5.25 (for vanadyl), 2.85-4.2 (for thorium) for 2 : 1 reaction.
- 3) In the higher pH range pK_2 values decrease but show constancy. This may be attributed to polymerisation, which is quite likely in the higher pH (alkaline) range.
- 4) The pK_3 values also show a decrease in the higher pH range but no constancy is observed. Existence of polymeric species is, therefore, doubtful.

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